

Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation

*Quality control scheme and metrics for the adaptive optics instruments
at the VLT*

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Leibundgut: Comment: During the VLT/AO Community Days past September, the issue arose of translating astronomical requirements to technical specifications of new instruments and the calibrations of existing instruments. A specific example is the new requirement of the stability of the PSF.

Yes, for some applications and science case it is not enough to have good peak performance, the standard deviation of the image quality (FWHM, Strehl) must be as small as possible and that's an indicator for stability. For large field AO instruments (GLAO, MCAO), the uniformity (or the knowledge of the non-uniformity) of the PSF across the FoV is of prime importance.

Roth: Comment: The importance of a factor of 2 energy concentration improvement with AOF for MUSE that you have mentioned for the science case e.g. of crowded fields - albeit very modest Strehl+FWHM improvement - is in fact dramatic. We have found from the analysis of data obtained under varying seeing conditions that the gain with 2x energy concentration in 0.2" spaxel is significant in terms of the number of useful spectra per field.

Yes, of course, I did not mean to say it was not impressive, it is just not impressive in terms of Strehl. Such "seeing improvement" (and it will be even more for the nights with a strong ground layer) opens tremendous possibility: get the same SNR in less time for a given program, get an improved SNR and FWHM (sharper images and better spectra) in the same on-source time. Finally, it will allow to go beyond the current capabilities of MUSE.